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REVIEW ON SARASWATI NIGHANTU

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Abstract

One of the key terms in the study of Dravyaguna Vijnana (Materia medica) is nighantu. The Nighantu can be characterized as a glossary that includes groups of synonyms, names of medications, plants, animals, minerals, and anything else that is given to the human body either as food or medicine. Saraswati Nighantu is one such Nighantu. For many generations, Sri- Lankan Ayurvedic students used this Nighantu as a textbook. But the author and time of this Nighantu is unknown. It consists of 6 *Varga* and a total of 349 *Dravya*. Classification of *Varga* is based mainly upon the habit of the plants. This Nighantu mainly describes the synonyms of the *Dravya*. The objective of this review is to analyse the importance and utility of Saraswati Nighantu.

Key Words:

Ayurveda, Saraswati Nighantu, Dravyaguna, Nighantu

INTRODUCTION:

According to Yaska, the Nighantu was a collection of rare or difficult words gathered by earlier sages for easier understanding of Vedic texts that perhaps they may not have fully understood themselves¹. But in ayurveda, the Nighantu (*Aushadhiya namakosha*) were composed for the better understanding of Samhita granth.

One such Nighantu is Saraswati Nighantu. This Nighantu was used as a textbook by the students of Ayurveda of Srilanka for many generations. But, due to mistakes of scribes, it has become vitiated. The present Saraswati Nighantu seems to be compiled in Srilanka (Ceylon) and hence it is very important in understanding the medicinal plants of South India and Srilanka.²

Author of Saraswati Nighantu³:

The name, period, and the date of the author of this Nighantu is not exactly known.

Method of Presentation:

There are two types of Ayurvedic Nighantus i.e. 1). Nighantus which has description of only synonyms of the dravya and 2). Nighantus which has description of synonyms as well as guna and karma of dravya. The Saraswati Nighantu is of first category. It has a description of total 349 dravya's synonyms only. These dravyas are divided into 6 varga which is based mainly upon the habit of the plant. The author has worshipped lord Narada-muni in the beginning of this beautiful work.

Varga: There is total 6 varga in Saraswati Nighantu. They are:

Table No. (1) List of Six Varga described in Saraswati Nighantu

No.	Varga Name
1.	Mahavrukshadi varga
2.	Kshupadi varga
3.	Ulapadi varga
4.	Latadi varga
5.	Chandanadi varga
6.	Bhaktadi varga

1). Mahavrukshadi Varga⁴:

In *Mahavrukshadi Varga*, the author of Saraswati Nighantu has included those medicinal plants which are big trees. It has total of 76 *Dravya*. They are:

Table No. (2) List of Dravya described in *Mahavrukshadi Varga*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Ashvattha</i>	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> Linn.	<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i> (Linn.) Kurz
<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> Corr.	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> (Gaertn.) Retz.
<i>Kapitha</i>	<i>Feronia elephantum</i> Correa.	<i>Bibhitaka</i>	<i>Terminalia bellerica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.
<i>Amra</i>	<i>Mangifera indica</i> Linn.	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Embllica officinalis</i> Gaertn.
<i>Chincha</i>	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> Linn.	<i>Ankola</i>	<i>Alangium salvifolium</i> (Linn. F.) Wang
<i>Arishta (Nimba)</i>	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	<i>Saptaparna</i>	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (Linn.) R. Br.
<i>Kaidarya</i>	<i>Murraya koenigi</i> (Linn) Spreng.	<i>Shakhota</i>	<i>Streblus asper</i> Lour.
<i>Katphala</i>	<i>Myrica esculenta</i> Buch.- Ham.	<i>Gojihva</i>	<i>Elephantopus scaber</i> Linn.
<i>Tuntuka (Shyonaka)</i>	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> Vent.	<i>Rajadan</i>	<i>Manilkara hexandra</i> (Roxb.) Dubard
<i>Aragvadha</i>	<i>Cassia fistula</i> Linn. & Willd.	<i>Plaksha</i>	<i>Ficus virens</i> Aiton
<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Madhuca indica</i> J.F. Gmel	<i>Vata</i>	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> Linn.
<i>Khadira</i>	<i>Acacia catechu</i> (Linn. F.) Willd.	<i>Udumbara</i>	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> Linn.
<i>Palasha</i>	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taub.	<i>Bhallataka</i>	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> Linn.f.
<i>Paribhadra</i>	<i>Erythrina indica</i> Lam.	<i>Shami</i>	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> Druce.
<i>Sarja</i>	<i>Vateria indica</i> Linn.	<i>Shleshmataka</i>	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> Forst.
<i>Varuna</i>	<i>Crataeva nurvala</i> Buch.- Ham.	<i>Tinisha</i>	<i>Ougenia dalbergioides</i> Benth.

<i>Kashmari</i> (<i>Gambhari</i>)	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Linn.	<i>Kovidara</i>	<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> Willd.
<i>Karanja</i>	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> Merr.	<i>Ashoka</i>	<i>Saraca asoca</i> (Roxb.) De Wilde.
<i>Putikaranja</i> (<i>Chirabilva</i>)	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia</i> Planch.	<i>Bakula</i>	<i>Mimusops elengi</i> Linn.
<i>Shalmali</i>	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> Linn.	<i>Champaka</i>	<i>Michelia champaka</i> Linn.
<i>Mocharasa</i>	<i>Exudation of Bombax ceiba</i> Linn.	<i>Nagakesara</i>	<i>Mesua ferrea</i> Linn.
<i>Kutaja</i>	<i>Holarrhena antidysenterica</i> (Roth) DC.	<i>Priyangu</i>	<i>Callicarpa macrophylla</i> Vahl.
<i>Indrayava</i>	Seeds of <i>Holarrhena</i> <i>antidysenterica</i> (Roth) DC.	<i>Punnaga</i>	<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i> Linn.
<i>Arjuna</i>	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb.) Wight.	<i>Karnikara</i>	<i>Pterospermum suberifolium</i> Linn.
<i>Kadamba</i>	<i>Mitragyna parviflora</i> (Roxb.) Korth.	<i>Akshiba</i>	-
<i>Patala</i>	<i>Stereospermum</i> <i>suaveolens</i> DC.	<i>Tilaka</i>	-
<i>Shigru</i>	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	<i>Badara</i>	<i>Ziziphus jujuba</i> Mill.
<i>Madhu-</i> <i>shigru</i>	<i>Moringa concanensis</i> Nimmo.	<i>Jambu</i>	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (Linn.) Skeels
<i>Agastya</i>	<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> Linn.	<i>Swetajambu</i>	<i>Syzygium malaccense</i> (Linn.) Merril & perry
<i>Putrajiva</i>	<i>Putranjiva roxburghii</i> Wall.	<i>Kakajambu</i>	
<i>Kataka</i>	<i>Strychnos potatorum</i> Linn.	<i>Panasa</i>	<i>Artocarpus integrifolia</i> Linn.f.
<i>Akshota</i>	<i>Juglans regia</i> Linn.	<i>Narikela</i>	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> Linn.

<i>Pilu</i>	<i>Salvadora persica</i> Linn.	<i>Tala</i>	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> Linn.
<i>Lodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos racemosa</i> Roxb.	<i>Kramuka</i>	<i>Areca catechu</i> Linn.
<i>Bhurja</i>	<i>Betula utilis</i> D. Don	<i>Vamsha</i>	<i>Bambusa aurundinacea</i> Willd.
<i>Shirisha</i>	<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (Linn.) Willd.	<i>Ketaki</i>	<i>Pandanus tectorius</i> Soland ex Park
<i>Vellantara (Virataru)</i>	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (Linn.) W. & A.	<i>Kharjura</i>	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (Linn.) Roxb.
<i>Tinduka</i>	<i>Diospyros melanoxyton</i> Roxb.	<i>Surapunnaga</i>	<i>Mammea suriga</i> (Ham. ex Roxb.) Kosterm

In *Mahavrukshadi Varga*, there is description of plants like *Akshiba* and *Tilaka* whose botanical identity is not yet clear. Also, there is a description of *Triphala* as *Haritaki*, *Amalaki* and *Bibhitaka*. Even though this *Varga* is named as *Mahavrukshadi Varga* and solely dedicated to the plants which are trees, still *Dhataki* (*Woodfordia fruticosa*) which is a shrub, is included in it. Also, there are some synonyms of plants which are described only in *Saraswati Nighantu*. Such as,

Table No. (3) List of synonyms mentioned only Saraswati Nighantu

Name of the plant	Synonym (s)
<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Nilamallika</i>
<i>Chincha</i>	<i>Vrukshamla</i>
<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Dolaphala</i>
<i>Karanja</i>	<i>Madhumakshipriya, manjaripushpaka</i>
<i>Rajadan</i>	<i>Vatsadani</i>
<i>Shami</i>	<i>Bhasmagarbha</i>
<i>Shleshmataka</i>	<i>Gudavruksha, mudgapatra</i>
<i>Tinisha</i>	<i>Gandharva, agnirandhram</i>
<i>Koyidara</i>	<i>Swarbhu, paara</i>
<i>Kharjuri</i>	<i>Nakshamaroha</i>

2). *Kshupadi Varga*⁵:

In these *Varga*, generally those plants are mentioned which are shrubs or small trees. This is the smallest *Varga* of *Saraswati Nighantu* and there is a total 35 *Dravya*. They are:

Table No. (4) List of Dravya described in *Kshupadi Varga*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Eranda</i>	<i>Ricinus communis</i> Linn.	<i>Japa</i>	<i>Hibiscus rosasinensis</i> Linn.
<i>Shephalika</i>	<i>Nyctanthes arbortristis</i> Linn.	<i>Bandhujiva</i>	<i>Pentapetes phoenicea</i> Linn.
<i>Nirgundi</i>	<i>Vitex negundo</i> Linn.	<i>Karavira</i>	<i>Nerium indicum</i> Mill.
<i>Aakuli</i>	-	<i>Bhanga</i>	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> Linn.
<i>Agnimantha</i>	<i>Clerodendrum phlomidis</i> Linn.	<i>Vasa</i>	<i>Adhatoda vasica</i> Nees.
<i>Karpasa</i>	<i>Gossypium herbaceum</i> Linn.	<i>Kasamarda</i>	<i>Cassia occidentalis</i> Linn.
<i>Arka</i>	<i>Calotropis Procera</i> (Ait.) R.Br.	<i>Kiratatikta</i>	<i>Swertia chirata</i> Buch.-Ham.
<i>Swetarka</i>	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (Linn.) Dryand	<i>Vishamushti</i>	<i>Strychnos nux vomica</i> Linn.
<i>Naranga</i>	<i>Citrus reticulata</i> Blanco	<i>Nagabala</i>	<i>Grewia populifolia</i> Vahl.
<i>Jambira</i>	<i>Citrus limon</i> Linn.	<i>Vartula</i>	-
<i>Likucha</i>	<i>Garcinia xanthochymus</i> Hook.f.	<i>Sahachara</i>	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> Linn.
<i>Matulunga</i>	<i>Citrus medica</i> Linn.	<i>Aartagala</i>	<i>Barleria strigose</i> Willd.
<i>Dadima</i>	<i>Punica granatum</i> Linn.	<i>Snuhi</i>	<i>Euphorbia nerifolia</i> Linn.
<i>Madana</i>	<i>Randia dumetorum</i> (Linn.) Lam.	<i>Patrasnuhi</i>	<i>Euphorbia nivulia</i> Buch.-Ham.
<i>Karamarda</i>	<i>Carissa congesta</i> Wight.	<i>Kadali</i>	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i> Linn. var. <i>sapientum</i> Kuntz.
<i>Nili</i>	<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> Linn.	<i>Vanakadali</i>	<i>Musa paradisiaca</i> Linn.
<i>Sharapunkha</i>	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> Linn.	<i>Ikshu</i>	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> Linn.
<i>Kantapunkha</i>	<i>Tephrosia</i> sp.		

In *Kshupadi Varga*, there is description of plants like *Aakuli* and *Vartula* whose botanical identity is unknown. There is a mention of two types of *Arka* (*Arka* and *Swetarka*), two types of *Sharaphunkha* (*Sharapunkha* and *Kantapunkha*), two types of *Sahachara* (*Sahachara* and *Aartagala*), two types of *Snuhi* (*Snuhi* and *Patrasnuhi*) and two types of *Kadali* (*Kadali* and *Vanakadali*).

3) *Ulapadi Varga*⁶:

In this *Varga*, the author has included mainly those plants which are herbs. This *Varga* contains a total of 74 *Dravya*. They are:

Table No. (5) List of Dravya described in *Ulapadi Varga*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Tulasi</i>	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> Willd.	<i>Pashanbheda</i>	<i>Saxifraga ligulata</i> Wall.
<i>Krushna tulsi</i>	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> Linn.	<i>Changeri</i>	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> Linn.
<i>Kutheraka</i>	<i>Orthosiphon spiralis</i> (Lour.) Merr.	<i>Dronapushpi</i>	<i>Leucas cephalotes</i> Spreng.
<i>Prachibala</i>	-	<i>Avakpushpi</i>	-
<i>Krushnarjaka</i>	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> Linn.	<i>Bhrungaraja</i>	<i>Eclipta alba</i> (Linn.) Hassk.
<i>Kakamachi</i>	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> Linn.	<i>Ikshugandha</i>	<i>Asteracantha longifolia</i> Nees.
<i>Gokshura</i>	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> Linn.	<i>Tamalaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus fraternus</i> Webster.
<i>Dhattura</i>	<i>Datura metel</i> Linn.	<i>Talapota</i>	-
<i>Apamarga</i>	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> Linn.	<i>Kumarika</i>	<i>Aloe vera</i> Tourn. Ex Linn.
<i>Danti</i>	<i>Baliospermum montanum</i> (Willd.) Muel-Arg.	<i>Patalamulika</i>	<i>Fagonia cretica</i> Linn.
<i>Balaa</i>	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> Linn.	<i>Vishmukranta</i>	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> Linn.
<i>Mahabalaa (Atibala)</i>	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (Linn.) SW.	<i>Kapotavanka / suvarchala</i>	<i>Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides</i> Lam.
<i>Bhumibalaa</i>	-	<i>Parpataka</i>	<i>Fumaria indica</i> Pugsley.
<i>Chitraka</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> Linn.	<i>Mugdaparni</i>	<i>Phaseolus trilobus</i> Ait.
<i>Marjaramohini</i>	-	<i>Mashaparni</i>	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i> (Linn.f.) Spreng.
<i>Chakramarda</i>	<i>Cassia tora</i> Linn. & Willd.	<i>Shalaparni</i>	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (Linn.) DC.
<i>Ashwagandha</i>	<i>Withania somnifera</i> Kaul	<i>Prushniparni</i>	<i>Uraria picta</i> Desv.
<i>Hapusha</i>	<i>Juniperus communis</i> Linn.	<i>Hamsapadi</i>	<i>Adiantum philippense</i> Linn.
<i>Mahamundi</i>	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> Linn.	<i>Mandukaparni</i>	<i>Centella asiatica</i> Linn.
<i>Mundi</i>	<i>Sphaeranthus africanus</i> Linn.	<i>Sunishannah</i>	<i>Celosia argentea</i> Linn.
<i>Sahadevi</i>	-	<i>Yavasa</i>	<i>Alhagi camelorum</i> Fisch.
<i>Bruhati</i>	<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm.f.	<i>Kusumbha</i>	<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i> Linn.
<i>Simhi</i>	<i>Solanum sp.</i>	<i>Durva</i>	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.
<i>Mahavartaki</i>	<i>Solanum sp.</i>	<i>Kusha/ Darbha</i>	<i>Desmostachya bipinnata</i> (Linn.) Stapf.
<i>Kshudra vartaki</i>			<i>Amorphophallus</i>

	<i>Solanum sp.</i>	<i>Surana</i>	<i>campanulatus Blume ex Decne.</i>
<i>Barbara</i>	<i>Cleome viscosa Linn.</i>	<i>Hastikarna</i>	<i>Plesmonium (Arum)(?)</i>
<i>Barbarika</i>	-	<i>Varahi</i>	<i>Dioscorea pentaphylla Linn.</i>
<i>Punarnava</i>	<i>Boerhavia repanda Linn.</i>	<i>Bhumitalika</i>	<i>Curculigo orchioides Gaertn.</i>
<i>Kshudra Punarnava</i>	<i>Boerhavia diffusa Linn.</i>	<i>Kamala</i>	<i>Nymphaea nauchali Burm.f.</i>
<i>Brahmi</i>	<i>Bacopa monnieri (Linn.) Pennel.</i>	<i>Swetakamala</i>	<i>Nymphaea sp.</i>
<i>Kapitha patra</i>	<i>Glinus oppositifolius (Linn.) A.DC.</i>	<i>Rakta-utpala</i>	<i>Nymphaea sp.</i>
<i>Vastuka</i>	<i>Chenopodium album Linn.</i>	<i>Nilotpala</i>	<i>Nymphaea sp.</i>
<i>Rakta vastuka</i>	<i>Chenopodium album Linn.</i>	<i>Kakotpala</i>	<i>Nymphaea sp.</i>
<i>Tanduliya</i>	<i>Amaranthus lividus Linn.</i>	<i>Raktakumuda</i>	<i>Nymphaea sp.</i>
<i>Chilli</i>	<i>Chenopodium album Linn.</i>	<i>Saugandhika</i>	<i>Nymphaea sp.</i>
<i>Saptala</i>	<i>Acacia concinna DC.</i>	<i>Shaivala</i>	<i>Ceratophyllum demesum Linn.</i>
<i>Traymana</i>	<i>Gentiana dahurica Fisch.</i>	<i>Variparni</i>	<i>Pistia stratiotes Linn.</i>

In this Varga, there is description of plants like Prachibala, Bhumbalaa, Marjarmohini, Barbarika, Sahadevi, Avakpushpi and Talapota whose botanical identity is not clear. Also, there is description of four types of Bruhati (Bruhati, Simhi, Mahavartaki and Kshudravartaki), two types of Punarnava (Punarnava and Kshudrapunarnava) and two types of Vastuka (Vastuka and Kshudravastuka). Also, varieties of Kamala are mentioned in this varga. Kusha and Darbha are mentioned as a synonym of single plant. Along with that, there is description of some synonyms of some plants which are not mentioned elsewhere. Such as,

Table No. (6) List of synonyms mentioned only Saraswati Nighantu

Name of the plant	Synonym (s)
<i>Kakamachi</i>	<i>Jaghanephala, Bahuphala, Sarpamari</i>
<i>Chakramarda</i>	<i>Vishanika, Kanaka</i>
<i>Ashwagandha</i>	<i>Kulangana</i>
<i>Pashanbheda</i>	<i>Udakoshmajita</i>
<i>Changeri</i>	<i>Hetuh, sunisannakpatrak</i>
<i>Bhrungaraja</i>	<i>Bhrungaparyayavachak, machalila</i>
<i>Ikshugandha</i>	<i>Gokshuraka</i>

4) **Latadi Varga**⁷:

Latadi Varga consists of those *Dravya* which are mainly climbers, creepers, etc. There are total of 45 *Dravya* in this *Varga*. They are:

Table No. (7) List of *Dravya* described in *Latadi Varga*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers.	<i>Kuberakshi</i>	<i>Caesalpinia bonducella</i> Fleming.
<i>Draksha</i>	<i>Vitis vinifera</i> Linn.	<i>Jyotishmati</i>	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i> Willd.
<i>Trivruta</i>	<i>Operculina turpethum</i> Silva Manso	<i>Kapikachhu</i>	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (Linn.) DC
<i>Shyama</i>		<i>Patha</i>	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> Linn.
<i>Bimbi</i>	<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (Linn.) Voigt.	<i>Langali</i>	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> Linn.
<i>Vidari</i>	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i> Roxb. ex Willd.	<i>Upodika</i>	<i>Basella alba</i> Linn.
<i>Ajashrungi</i>	<i>Gymnema sylvestris</i> R.Br.	<i>Kushmandaki</i>	<i>Benincasa cerifera</i> Savi.
<i>Murva</i>	<i>Marsdenia tenacissima</i> W. & A.	<i>Tumbi</i>	<i>Lagenaria siceraria</i> (Molina) Standl.
<i>Shatamuli (Shatavari)</i>	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	<i>Katutumbi</i>	<i>Lagenaria siceraria</i> (Molina) Standl.
<i>Nyagrodhi</i>	<i>Jatropha glandulifera</i> Roxb.	<i>Koshataki</i>	<i>Luffa acutangular</i> Roxb.
<i>Tambuli</i>	<i>Piper betle</i> Linn.	<i>Katukoshataki</i>	<i>Luffa acutangular</i> Roxb. var. <i>amara</i> Clarke.
<i>Vajravalli</i>	-	<i>Karkati</i>	<i>Cucumis utilisimus</i> Roxb.
<i>Lakshmana</i>	<i>Ipomoea sepiaria</i> Koen.	<i>Indravaruni</i>	<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> (Linn.) Schrad.
<i>Sharangesta</i>	-	<i>Trapusa</i>	<i>Trichosanthes palmata</i> Roxb.
<i>Patola</i>	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i> Roxb.	<i>Karkoti</i>	<i>Momordica dioica</i> Rocb. ex Willd.
<i>Somavalli</i>	<i>Ephedra gerardiana</i> Wall.	<i>Karavalli</i>	<i>Momordica charantia</i> Linn.

<i>Devadali</i>	<i>Luffa echinata Roxb.</i>	<i>Sprukka</i>	<i>Mellilotus officinalis (Linn.) Medik.</i>
<i>Prasarini</i>	<i>Paederia foetida Linn.</i>	<i>Mallika</i>	<i>Jasminum sambuc Linn.</i>
<i>Girikarni (Aparajita)</i>	<i>Clitoria ternatea Linn.</i>	<i>Malati</i>	<i>Jasminum grandiflorum Linn.</i>
<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Berberis aristata DC.</i>	<i>Madhavilata</i>	<i>Hiptage benghalensis (Linn.) Kurz.</i>
<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Curcuma longa Linn.</i>	<i>Yuthika</i>	<i>Jasminum auriculatum Vahl.</i>
<i>Sariva</i>	<i>Hemidesmus indicus (Linn.) R.Br.</i>	<i>Tilaka</i>	-
<i>Gunja</i>	<i>Abrus precatorius Linn.</i>		

In this *Varga*, there is description of plants like *Vajravalli*, *Sharangesta* and *Tilaka* whose botanical identity is not known. *Vidari* and *Ikshuvidarika* are mentioned as synonyms. And *Koshataki* and *Katukoshataki* are mentioned as different plants. Along with that, there is description of some synonyms of some plants which are not mentioned elsewhere. Such as,

Table No. (8) List of synonyms mentioned only Saraswati Nighantu

Name of the plant	Synonym (s)
<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Sukshmapatra</i>
<i>Daruharidra</i>	<i>Hemaharitaka</i>

5) Chandanadi Varga⁸:

The fifth *Varga* of Saraswati Nighantu is *Chandanadi*, which is mainly comprised of aromatic plants. But, along with aromatic plants, there is a description of mineral *Dravya* also. These *Varga* has a total of 119 *Dravya*, making it the largest *Varga* of an entire Nighantu. The *Dravya* of *Chandanadi Varga* includes:

Table No. (9) List of Dravya described in *Chandanadi Varga*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Sweta Chandana</i>	<i>Santalum album</i> Linn.	<i>Sauvarchala</i>	Black salt
<i>Hari Chandana</i>	<i>Santalum album</i> Linn.	<i>Sarjikakshara</i>	Impure carbonate of soda
<i>Rakta Chandana</i>	<i>Santalum album</i> Linn.	<i>Vid lavana</i>	Type of salt
<i>Aguru</i>	<i>Aquillaria agallocha</i> Roxb.	<i>Kala lavana</i>	Type of salt
<i>Kalaguru</i>	<i>Aquillaria agallocha</i> Roxb.	<i>Samudra lavana</i>	Type of salt
<i>Sugandhaguru</i>	<i>Aquillaria agallocha</i> Roxb.	<i>Panshu lavana</i>	Type of salt
<i>Devadaru</i>	<i>Cedrus deodara</i> Roxb. ex D.Don	<i>Roma lavana</i>	Type of salt
<i>Karpura</i>	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> (Linn.) Sieb.	<i>Audbhida lavana</i>	Type of salt
<i>Kasturi</i>	Secretion from the Musk deer	<i>Yavakshara</i>	Impure carbonate of potash
<i>Kumkum</i>	<i>Crocus sativus</i> Linn.	<i>Sarkara</i>	Sugar
<i>Shrivasa</i>	Oleoresin of <i>Pinus longifolia</i>	<i>Khandas harkara</i>	Form of Sugar
<i>Sarjarasa</i>	Resin of <i>Shora robusta</i> Gaertn.f.	<i>Phanita</i>	
<i>Guggulu</i>	<i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Arnott) Bhandari.	<i>Kshaudra</i>	Honey
<i>Rochana</i>	Bovine gall stone	<i>Siktha</i>	Bees wax
<i>Kustha</i>	<i>Sausurrea lappa</i> (Decne.) Sch. Bip.	<i>Laksha</i>	Lac
<i>Tagara</i>	<i>Valeriana wallichii</i> DC.	<i>Gairika</i>	Ochre
<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhica glabra</i> Linn.	<i>Parada</i>	Mercury
<i>Ushira</i>		<i>Hingula</i>	Cinnabar

<i>Hribera</i>	<i>Vetiveria zizanoides</i> (Linn.) Nash	<i>Haratala</i>	Orpiment
<i>Kankola</i>	<i>Piper cubeba</i> Linn. F.	<i>Manahshila</i>	Realgar
<i>Nagakesara</i>	<i>Mesua ferrea</i> Linn.	<i>Gandhak</i> <i>a</i>	Sulphur
<i>Ela</i>	<i>Amomum subulatum</i> Roxb.	<i>Karpuri</i> <i>tuttha</i>	Blue vitriol
<i>Sukshma ela</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> (Linn.) Maton.	<i>Mayura</i> <i>tuttha</i>	Copper sulphate
<i>Tvak</i>	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J.S. Presl.	<i>Sroto</i> <i>Anjana</i>	Galena
<i>Tamalapatra</i>	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i> (Ham.) Nees & Eburm.	<i>Kapota</i> <i>Anjana</i>	Type of Anjana
<i>Jatiphala</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt.	<i>Darvi</i> <i>Anjana</i>	Type of Anjana
<i>Lavanga</i>	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (Linn.) Merr. & L.M. Perry	<i>Rasanjana</i> <i>a</i>	Type of Anjana
<i>Jatipatri</i>	Aril of Nutmeg	<i>Sindura</i>	Red lead
<i>Choraka</i>	<i>Angelica glauca</i> Edg.	<i>Makshika</i>	Chalcopyrite
<i>Dwitiya choraka</i>	-	<i>Sweta</i> <i>pashana</i>	Kind of stone
<i>Nakha</i>	-	<i>Shilajatu</i>	Black bitumen
<i>Manjistha</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i> Linn.	<i>Vatsnabh</i> <i>a</i>	<i>Aconitum ferox</i> Wall. ex ser.
<i>Bakuchi</i>	<i>Psoralea cordifolia</i> Linn.	<i>Ayaskant</i> <i>a</i>	Magnet
<i>Jatamansi</i>	<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i> DC.	<i>Abhraka</i>	Mica
<i>Musta</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn.	<i>Samudra</i> <i>phena</i>	Os sepiae
<i>Rasna</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i> Oliver	<i>Tankana</i>	Borax
<i>Shatapushpa</i>	<i>Peucedanum graveolens</i> Linn.	<i>Varata</i>	Cowrie
<i>Vidanga</i>	<i>Embelia ribes</i> Burm.f.	<i>Mauktika</i>	Pearl

<i>Ativisha</i>	<i>Aconitum heterophyllum</i> <i>Wall. ex Royle</i>	<i>Pravala</i>	Coral
<i>Katurohini</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i> Royle ex <i>Benth.</i>	<i>Padmara</i> <i>ga</i>	Ruby
<i>Pitarohini</i>	-	<i>Gomeda</i>	Hessonite
<i>Prapaundrika</i>	-	<i>Hiraka</i>	Diamond
<i>Shankhanakha</i>	-	<i>Vaidurya</i>	Cat's eye
<i>Vansharochana</i>	<i>Bambusa aurundinaceae</i> <i>Willd.</i>	<i>Indranila</i>	Blue sapphire
<i>Dhanyaka</i>	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i> Linn.	<i>Pushpara</i> <i>ga</i>	Yellow sapphire
<i>Jiraka</i>	<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> Linn.	<i>Markata</i>	Emerald
<i>Krushna jiraka</i>	<i>Carum carvi</i> Linn.	<i>Suryakan</i> <i>ta</i>	Spinel
<i>Ajamoda</i>	<i>Trachyspermum</i> <i>roxburghianum</i> (DC.) <i>Craib.</i>	<i>Chandrak</i> <i>anta</i>	Moonstone
<i>Sarsapa</i>	<i>Brassica juneca</i> Roxb.	<i>Yavaksha</i> <i>ra</i>	Impure carbonate of potash
<i>Sweta sarsapa</i>	<i>Brassica campestris</i> Linn.	<i>Suvarna</i>	Gold
<i>Shunthi</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	<i>Rupyaka</i>	Silver
<i>Maricha</i>	<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn.	<i>Tamra</i>	Copper
<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn.	<i>Riti</i>	Brass
<i>Gajapippali</i>	<i>Piper retrofactum</i> Vahl.	<i>Kamshya</i>	Bronze
<i>Pippalimula</i>	Roots of <i>Piper longum</i> Linn.	<i>Sisa</i>	Lead
<i>Hingu</i>	<i>Ferula asafoetida</i> Linn.	<i>Vanga</i>	Tin
<i>Methi</i>	<i>Trigonella foenum-</i> <i>graecum</i> Linn.	<i>Tikshnalo</i> <i>ha</i>	Type of iron
<i>Rasona</i>	<i>Allium sativum</i> Linn.	<i>Loha</i>	Iron

<i>Grunjana</i>	<i>Allium ascalonicum</i> Linn.	<i>Mandura</i>	Iron rust
<i>Saindhav</i>	<i>Rock salt</i>		

In this *Varga*, total 58 Plants, 2 Animal origin *Dravya* (*Kasturi* and *Rochana*) and 59 Mineral *Dravya* are mentioned. There is description of plants like *Nakha*, *Shankhanakha*, *Prapaundrika* and *Pitarohini* whose botanical identification is not clear / controversial. Also, there is description of *Trijata*, *Chaturjata*, *Trikatu*, *Lavanashtaka*, *Navaratna* and *Panchloha*. Along with that, there is mentioning of three types of *Chandana* (*Chandana*, *Harichandana* and *Raktachandana*), three types of *Agaru* (*Agaru*, *Sugandhagaru* and *Kalagaru*), two types of *Ela* (*Ela* and *Sukshma-ela*), two types of *Jeeraka* (*Jeeraka* and *Krushna-Jeeraka*) and two types of *Choraka* (*Choraka* and *Dwitiya-choraka*). *Lamajjaka* and *Ushira*; and *Sarsapa* and *Rajika* are mentioned as a synonymous to each other.

6. Bhaktadi Varga⁹:

This is the last *varga* of Saraswati Nighantu. This *Varga* describes about synonyms of food and food articles like different *dhanyas*. It includes:

Table No. (10) List of *Dravya* described in *Bhaktadi Varga*

Sanskrit name	Latin / English name	Sanskrit name	Latin / English name
<i>Bhakta</i>	Food	<i>Ghrita</i>	Clarified butter
<i>Dagdha bhakta</i>	Burnt food	<i>Gomutra</i>	Cow's urine
<i>Mashara</i>		<i>Goshakruta</i>	Cow's feces
<i>Ghana and yavagu</i>	Boiled liquid rice	<i>Dadhiyadi</i>	Curd, etc.
<i>Tandula</i>	Rice	<i>Sudha</i>	Divine nectar(?)
<i>Laja</i>		<i>Rudhira</i>	Blood
<i>Kanjika</i>	Sour gruel	<i>Vruksha</i>	Tree
<i>Tandulodaka</i>	Rice water	<i>Lata</i>	Twiner
<i>Vari</i>	Water	<i>Mula</i>	Roots
<i>Godhuma</i>	Triticum sativum Linn.	<i>Kanda</i>	Tuber
<i>Kodrava</i>	Paspalum scrobiculatum Linn.	<i>Patra</i>	Leaves
<i>Kangu</i>	Setaria italica Beauv.	<i>Valakala and Samita</i>	Bark
<i>Mudga</i>	Phaseolus radiata Linn.	<i>Pushpa</i>	Flower
<i>Kulattha</i>	Dolichus uniflorus	<i>Kalika</i>	Bud

	Lamk.		
<i>Rajamasha</i>	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> Linn.	<i>Bala phala</i>	Immature fruit
<i>Masha</i>	<i>Vigna mungo</i> (Linn.) Hepper	<i>Phala & sushka</i> <i>phala</i>	Fruit and dried fruit
<i>Chanaka</i>	<i>Cicer arietinum</i> Linn.	<i>Niryasa</i>	Exudate
<i>Tila</i>	<i>Sesamum indicum</i> Linn.	<i>Naala, Vrunta</i>	
<i>Tila-taila</i>	Oil of seeds of <i>Sesamum indicum</i> Linn.	<i>Beeja</i>	Seeds
<i>Kshira</i>	Milk	<i>Roga</i>	Disease
<i>Dadhi and mastu</i>	Curd	<i>Aatura</i>	Patient
<i>Takra</i>	Buttermilk	<i>Bhishak</i>	Physician
<i>Navanita</i>	Butter	<i>Arogya</i>	Health

This varga describes about food articles, along with that it has description of synonyms of various parts of the plants. Also, there is mentioning of *Panchanga* (five parts of the plants) including *Mula*, *Patra*, *Phala*, *Pushpa* and *Twaka*. And there is also a description of *Roga*, *Atura*, *Bhishak* and *Arogya* at the end of this Nighantu.

DISCUSSION:

The name, period, and the date of the author of the Saraswati Nighantu is not exactly known¹⁰. But the author of the book 'Studies on Medicinal Plants & Drugs in Saraswati Nighantu' by Dr. S. D. Kamat, has written in his book preface that, the Mss from Colombo is available at Anandasram Mudranalaya, Pune¹¹. The source mss. was prepared for printing after being edited by J. P. Jayatilak¹². He had provided information about this Nighantu and stated that the author, period, and the date of the compiler of this Nighantu is not exactly known. It was used as a textbook by the students of Ayurveda of Shrilanka for many generations. But due to mistakes of scribes (copy writers) it has become vitiated. The importance of this Nighantu is that it contains many new plants and synonyms which are not found in other Nighantus¹³.

The book 'Studies on Medicinal Plants & Drugs in Saraswati Nighantu' describes about total of 6 varga, first 4 varga are mainly divided based upon the habit of the plant, 5th varga consists of aromatic plants, drugs obtained from animal origin and mineral origin drugs. And total 349 dravya, along with their botanical identity. There are some dravya like *Akshiba*, *Tilaka*, *Aakuli*, *Vartula*, etc. in which it is stated that the botanical identity is not clear. Thus, in this article, the botanical source of those plants whose botanical identity is not clear or is controversial are not mentioned.

It also consists of synonyms of some plants which are not described in any other Nighantu, such as, *Bilva (Nilamallika)*, *Chincha (Vrukshamla)*, *Madhuka (Dolaphala)*, *Karanja (Madhumakshipriya)*, *Manjaripushpaka*, *Rajadan (Vatsadani)*, *Shami (Bhasmagarbha)*, *Shleshmataka (Gudavruksha, Mudgapatra)*, *Tinisha (Gandharva, Agnirandhram)*, *Kovidara (Swarbhu, Paara)*, *Kharjuri (Nakshamaroha)*, etc. In the last *Varga*, there is description of *Panchanga, Roga, Atura, Bhishak, and Arogya*.

CONCLUSION:

Saraswati Nighantu comprises of synonyms of the dravya. The author's name, period and the date of this Nighantu is not known. This Nighantu will be very beneficial to scholars, students, and researchers studying Ayurvedic medicinal plants if all the plants mentioned in it are correctly identified with the assistance of botanists and Ayurvedic physicians.

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